

KNOWLEDGE ON PREVENTION OF SEXUALLY TRANSMITTED INFECTIONS AMONG SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS SEEKING HEALTHCARE SERVICES IN JERE LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA, BORNO STATE, NIGERIA

BY

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17633184>

Abstract

This study was conducted to assess knowledge on prevention of sexually transmitted infections among secondary school students seeking healthcare services in Jere Local Government Area, Borno State. Two (2) objectives were raised, two (2) research questions were answered and two (2) hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. A cross-sectional research design was used for the study. The population of this study comprises of (2678) secondary school students population seeking healthcare services, a sample of two hundred and sixty-five (265) was used, four (4) healthcare facilities were selected using purposive sampling techniques. Fifteen (15) item self-developed questionnaire was used with a reliability index of 0.841 which indicated that the instrument is reliable. Descriptive statistics of frequency counts, percentages mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions while inferential statistics of independent t-test was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The results of the study indicated that there is significant knowledge of secondary school students on use of condoms for the prevention of sexually transmitted infections in Jere Local Government based on gender ($t=4.7704$; $p = 0.00$) and there is significant knowledge of secondary school students on abstinence for the prevention of sexually transmitted infections in Jere Local Government based on gender ($t = 5.9110$; $p = 0.00$). In conclusion, there is knowledge of adolescents on use of condoms and abstinence as a measure for the prevention of sexually transmitted infections among secondary school students in Jere Local Government based on gender. It was recommended that, Jere Local Government Primary health care clinics should continue to enlighten adolescents on the basic knowledge of prevention against sexual transmitted infections (STIs) to secondary school students and Jere Local Government Council should partnership with NGOs to provide adequate condoms for the prevention of STIs as knowledge of adolescents on the use of condoms as prevention of sexual transmitted infections (STIs) appropriate.

Keywords: Knowledge, Sexually Transmitted Infections (STI), Secondary School Students

Introduction:

Sexually transmitted infections (STIs) are a broad category of contagious diseases that are widespread all over the globe and are mainly contracted through sexual interactions. Sexually transmitted infections (STIs) are a variety of clinical syndromes caused by pathogens that can be acquired and transmitted through sexual contact. There are over 30 bacterial, viral, and parasitic pathogens that have been identified to date to be transmitted sexually (World Health Organisation, 2017). Sexually transmitted infections are a major public health problem worldwide that cause acute illness, long-term complication, infertility, certain cancers, and other chronic disease medical conditions, as well as psychological consequences and death,

particularly in higher and low-income countries, including Nigeria (WHO, 2017).

Knowledge on the prevention of sexually transmitted infections (STIs) are major priorities for public health and preventive medicine in the industrial world, despite the fact that the spread rates of sexually transmitted infections (STIs) transmission among adolescents is more catastrophic in the developing countries like Nigeria, than in developed countries (World Health Organisation, 2016). Knowledge on prevention of sexually transmitted infections (STIs) is a cornerstone of public health diseases preventive measure through behavioural intervention of “ABC” which stand (Abstinence, Be-honest and Condoms use) (Gulnara, Man, Saltanat, Raikhan, Gulzada, & Baizhol 2017).

Knowledge on preventive measure of (STIs) are major concern of public health, particularly for the secondary school students age as well as adolescents population in generally. The increasing trend of sexually transmitted infections (STIs) among adolescents population is an alarming issue, as they are among the major contributors for (STIs) cases worldwide (Centre for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC, 2018)). World Health Organization has been performing a worldwide estimation for four curable (STIs) approximately every five years since 2015 (Rowley, Vander, Korenromp, Low, Unemo, Abu-Raddad 2019).

Sexually transmitted infections (STIs) are preventable diseases, but the rates at which some (STIs) continues to increase, particularly among young people, which required urgent intervention on educational sensitization and awareness (Health Protection Agency, 2018). Secondary school students might be at risk for (STIs) as a result of a variety of reasons, such as inadequate knowledge about mean (STIs) prevention, ignorance about sexual abstinence, low self-efficacy (lacking belief that one can successfully meet a goal or perform a particular task such as using condoms), poor condom use and/or sexual negotiation skills, and having sex with multiple partner (Goya, 2018).

Adolescents are more likely to practice unprotected sex, have multiple sexual partners, and have Tran's generational and transactional sex. On adolescents knowledge on the prevention of STLs, parents play a pivotal role in educating and supervising young children about sexual education. But in Nigeria, culture has been one of the factors causing communication gaps between parents and children to discuss topics related to sex and sexual education (Akande, 2019). However, parents and family are critical in keeping adolescents safe. Perceived family support, parent-family

connectedness, family structure, family cohesiveness, parental monitoring and parent adolescent communication about sex help to prevent and improved adolescents knowledge from engaging in many risky sexual behaviours (Akande, 2019). Therefore, it's against this background that, this study sought to assessed knowledge on prevention of sexually transmitted infections among secondary school students seeking healthcare services in Jere Local Government Area, Borno State, Nigeria.

Objectives of the Study

The objectives of this study are to assessed:

1. Knowledge on the use of condom for the prevention of sexually transmitted infections among secondary school students seeking healthcare services in Jere Local Government Area.
2. Knowledge of sexual abstinence as a measure for preventing sexually transmitted infections among secondary school students seeking healthcare services in Jere Local Government Area.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What is the knowledge on the use of condom for the prevention of sexually transmitted infections among secondary school students seeking healthcare services in Jere Local Government Area?
2. What knowledge of sexual abstinence do secondary school students know as a measure for preventing sexually transmitted infections among adolescents seeking healthcare services in Jere Local Government Area?

Hypotheses

H0₁: There is no significant knowledge of secondary school students on use of condoms for the prevention of sexually transmitted infections in Jere Local Government based on gender.

H0₂: There is no significant knowledge of secondary school students on sexual abstinence for the prevention of sexually transmitted infections in Jere Local Government based on gender.

Methodology

A cross sectional research design of survey method was used for the study. The study population comprised a total of (2678) secondary school age (adolescents) seeking healthcare services in Jere Local Government primary healthcare facilities. A sample of two hundred and sixty-five (265) was used, four (4) healthcare facilities was purposively selected using purposive sampling techniques namely, Mashamari Primary Healthcare, Goni Kachallari Primary Healthcare, Maimusari Primary Healthcare, and Old Maiduguri Primary

Healthcare Clinic. Data were collected using fifteen (15) item self-developed questionnaire, using a four-point modified Likert type scale with response modes of “Strongly Agree (SA) 4 points, Agree (A) 3 points, Disagree (D) 2 points, and Strongly Disagree (SD) 1 point”, with a reliability index of 0.841 which indicated that the instrument is reliable. Descriptive statistics of frequency counts, percentages, mean and standard deviation were used to described the demographic characteristics of the respondents and answer the research questions while inferential statistics of independent t-test was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

Results

Descriptive statistics of frequency counts and percentages, mean and standard deviation were used to described the demographic characteristics of the respondents and to answer the research questions while inferential statistics of independent t-test was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of the Respondents

n=265				
S/N	Variables	Responses	Respondents	Percentage (%)
1.	Age	a. 10-15 years	119	44.9
		b. 16-18 years	146	55.1
2.	Gender	a. Male	124	46.7
		b. Female	141	53.3
3.	Educational Qualification	a. No Formal Education	34	12.8
		b. Primary Leaving Certificate	73	27.5
		c. JSSCE	128	48.3
		d. SSCE	30	11.4

The result in table 1 contains the demographic characteristics of the respondents. Three variables were displayed in the table namely age, gender, educational qualification and attending healthcare facility. The breakdown of age of the respondents shows that majority of the respondents 146(55.1%) were fall within the

age bracket of 16-18years while 119(55.1%) were within the age range of 10-15years. Gender of the respondents, the finding shows that majority of the respondents 141(53.2%) were female while 124(46.7%) were male. On the educational qualification the findings of the study show that, majority of the respondents 128(48.3%) were obtained JSSCE, 73(27.5%)

were obtained first primary leaving certificate, 34(12.8%) were not attended any formal

education while 30(11.4%) were obtained SSCE.

Research Question 1

What are the knowledge on the use of condom for the prevention of sexually transmitted infections among adolescents seeking healthcare services in Jere Local Government Area?

Table 2 Responses of Secondary School Students Seeking Healthcare Services in Jere Local Government Area on the Knowledge on use of Condom for the Prevention of Sexually Transmitted Infections

		n=265						
S/N	Variables		SA	A	D	SD	Mean	SD
4.	Condoms is used to prevent contraction of STIs.	F %	144 54.4	97 36.6	20 7.4	4 1.6	2.79	.671
5	Condoms did not only prevent STIs but also prevent un-planned pregnancy.	F %	114 43.1	89 33.6	43 16.2	19 7.1	2.65	.943
6.	Sexually transmitted infections contracted by having sex without protective device such as condoms.	F %	186 70.1	67 25.5	9 3.3	186 70.1	2.40	.490
7.	I know that condoms are safe in preventing STIs.	F %	173 65.3	59 22.3	23 8.7	173 65.3	3.32	.808
8.	Having sex without condom used led to contraction of STIs.	F %	152 57.4	96 36.3	12 4.5	152 57.4	2.83	.883
9.	I know that adolescents use of condom during sex related activities	F %	204 77	43 16.9	12 4.5	6 2.2	3.12	.668

Keys: SA= Strongly Agree, A= Agree, D= Disagree, SD= Strongly Disagree

Table 2 above shows the responses of secondary school students seeking healthcare services in Jere Local Government area on the knowledge on the use of condom for the prevention of sexually transmitted infections. The findings of the study on item 4 shows that, majority of the respondents 144(54.4%) were strongly agreed that, condom is used to prevent contraction of STIs, 97(36.6%) were agreed, 20(7.6%) were disagreed while 4(1.6%) were strongly disagreed. Item 5 in the table also shows that majority of the respondents 114(43.1%) were strongly agreed that, condoms did not only prevent STIs but also prevent un-planned pregnancy, 89(33.6%) were agreed, 43(16.2%) were disagreed while 19(7.1%) were

strongly disagreed with the statement. Item 6 also shows that majority of the respondents 209(78.9%) were strongly agreed that, sexually transmitted infections are contracted by having sex without protective device such as condoms, 38(14.3%) were agreed, 15(5.7%) were disagreed while 3(1.1%) were strongly disagreed with the statement. Item 7 in the table further shows that majority of the respondents, 186(70.1%) were strongly agreed, 67(25.2%) were agreed, 09(3.3%) were disagreed while 3(1.1%) were strongly disagreed. Item 8 in the table also shows that majority of the respondents, 173(65.2%) were strongly agreed that, having sex without used of condom would led to contraction of STIs, 59(22.3%) were agreed,

23(8.7%) were disagreed while 10(3.7%) were strongly disagreed with the statement. Item 9 in the table also shows that majority of the respondents, 152(57.4%) were strong agreed that, they knew that adolescents used condom

during sex related activities, 96(36.3%) were agreed, 12(4.5%) were disagreed while 5(1.8%) were strongly disagreed with the statement.

Research Question 2

What knowledge of sexual abstinence do secondary school students know as a measure for preventing sexually transmitted infections among adolescents seeking healthcare services in Jere Local Government Area?

Table 4.4 Responses of Secondary School Students Seeking Healthcare Services in Jere Local Government Area on the Knowledge of Sexual Abstinence as a Measure for Preventing Sexually Transmitted Infections

				n=265					
S/N	Variables		SA	A	D	SD	Mean	SD	
10.	I know staying away from sex related activities like kissing prevent contraction of STIs	F %	164 61.9	89 33.6	8 3	4 1.5	2.75	.488	
11.	Been honesty to sex partner prevent contraction of STIs.	F %	74 27.9	69 26.1	64 24.2	58 21.8	2.77	.479	
12.	Withdrawal of self from friends who involve sex activities prevent contraction of STIs.	F %	209 78.9	44 16.7	9 3.3	3 1.1	2.61	.584	
13.	Staying away from sex related video clip pictures prevent individual from risk contrac STIs.	F %	186 70.1	67 25.2	9 3.6	3 1.1	2.49	.494	
14.	Having multiple sex partner let to contraction of STIs.	F %	163 61.5	69 26.1	23 8.7	10 3.7	2.28	.629	
15.	I know that practice of “ABC” prevent contraction of STIs.	F %	132 49.9	116 43.8	12 4.5	5 1.8	3.12	.668	

Keys: SA= Strongly Agree, A= Agree, D= Disagree, SD= Strongly Disagree.

The result in table 3 above shows the responses of secondary school students seeking healthcare services in Jere Local Government area on the knowledge of sexual abstinence as a measure for preventing sexually transmitted infections. The findings of the study on item 10 shows that, majority of the respondents 164(61.9%) were strongly agreed that, they knew that staying away from sex related activities like kissing prevent contraction of STIs, 89(33.6%) were agreed, 08(3.0%) were disagreed while 04(1.5%) were strongly disagreed with the statement. Item 11 in

the table also shows that, majority of the respondents 74(27.9%) were strongly agreed that, been honesty to sex partner prevent contraction of STIs, 69(26.1%) were agreed, 64(24.2%) were disagreed while 58(21.8%) were strongly disagreed. The findings of the study on item 12 in the table further shows that, majority of the respondents 209(78.9%) were strongly agreed that, withdrawal of self from friends who involves in sex activities prevent contraction of STIs, 44(16.7%) were agreed, while 12(4.5%) were disagreed and strongly disagreed respectively. Item 13 in the table also shows that,

majority of the respondents, 186(70.1%) were strongly agreed that, staying away from sex related video clip and pictures prevent individual from risk contracting STIs, 67(25.2%) were agreed while 12(4.5%) were disagreed and strongly disagreed with the statement respectively. Item 14 in the table also shows that, majority of the respondents 163(61.5%) were strongly agreed that, having multiple sex partner would have led to contraction of STIs, 69(26.1%) were agreed 23(8.7%) were disagreed 10(3.7%) were strongly disagreed with the statement. Item 15 in the table also shows that, majority of the

respondents 132(49.9%) were strongly agreed that, they knew that practice of “ABC” prevent contraction of STIs, 116(43.8%) were agreed, 12(4.5%) were disagreed 5(1.8%) were strongly disagreed with the statement.

Hypothesis

H0₁: There is no significant knowledge of secondary school students on use of condoms for the prevention of sexually transmitted infections in Jere Local Government based on gender.

Table 4: Results of Independent t test on the knowledge of secondary school students on use of condoms for the prevention of sexually transmitted infections based on gender

n= 265						
Gender	Mean	SD	df	t	p-value	Decision
Male	23.0114	6.2571	263	4.7704	0.00	Null hypothesis Rejected
Female	19.6017	4.0143				

The result in table above showed that, male and female result on the knowledge of adolescents on use of condoms for the prevention of sexually transmitted infections. The p value 0.00 is less than 0.05 level of significance and the t calculated 4.7704 is greater than t critical of 2.028. Therefore, the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant knowledge of secondary school students on use of condoms for the prevention of sexually transmitted

infections in Jere Local Government based on gender is hereby rejected. This means that there is significant knowledge of secondary school students on use of condoms for the prevention of sexually transmitted infections in Jere Local Government based on gender.

H0₂: There is no significant knowledge of secondary school students on sexual abstinence for the prevention of sexually transmitted infections in Jere Local Government based on gender.

Table 5: Results of Independent t test on the knowledge of secondary school students on sexual abstinence for the prevention of sexually transmitted infections based on gender

n= 265						
Gender	Mean	SD	Df	t	p-value	Decision
Male	17.0343	3.8519	263	5.9110	0.00	Null hypothesis Rejected
Female	18.9059	3.1007				

The result in table 5 above showed the male and female result on the knowledge of secondary school students on sexual abstinence for the prevention of sexually transmitted infections. The p value 0.00 is less than 0.05 level of

significance and the t calculated 5.9110 is greater than t critical of 2.028. Therefore, the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant knowledge of secondary school students on sexual abstinence for the prevention

of sexually transmitted infections in Jere Local Government based on gender is hereby rejected. This means that there is significant knowledge of adolescents on abstinence for the prevention of sexually transmitted infections in Jere Local Government based on gender.

Discussion of Findings

This study was conducted to assess knowledge on prevention of sexually transmitted infections secondary school students seeking healthcare services in Jere Local Government Area, Borno State, Nigeria. The result of the study shows that, there was a significant knowledge of adolescents on use of condoms for the prevention of sexually transmitted infections in Jere Local Government based on gender. This finding is in line with that of James, (2018) found that, males and females adolescent had previous knowledge and experiences of condom used was correlated positively with current use condoms as a measure for preventing STIs. Zhao, Zhang, Fu, Su and Zhang (2019) also found on survey of adolescent sexual and reproductive health knowledge of prevention of sexual transmitted infections (STIs) found that, adolescents who had sex 58% had knowledge on how to use condoms while 31% are not practice preventive measure.

The result of this study further indicated, on knowledge of secondary school students on sexual abstinence for the prevention of STIs, the study found that, there was a significant knowledge of secondary school students on sexual abstinence for the prevention of sexually transmitted infections in Jere Local Government based on gender. The finding of this finding study is in agreement with that of Health Protection Agency, (2018) stated that, adolescents who practice sexual abstinence are less likely to contract STIs and less likely to developed depression, attempt suicide, live in

poverty as adults and are likely to do better in school.

Recommendation

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Jere Local Government Council should partnership with NGOs to provide adequate condoms for the prevention of STIs as knowledge of secondary school students on the use of condoms as prevention of sexual transmitted infections (STIs) appropriate.
2. Healthcare workers in the primary healthcare clinics should continue to provide adequate health talks as knowledge of adolescents on abstinence for the prevention of sexually transmitted infections in Jere Local Government adequate.

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